

Studies in Ion-exchange Equilibria. Part II. Exchange of Univalent Anions on Amberlite IR-4B and Amberlite IRA-410

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The equilibrium studies have been performed on a weakly basic anion exchanger (Amberlite IR-4B) and a strongly basic anion exchanger (Amberlite IRA-410) in hydroxyl form with univalent anions (F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , and NO_3^-). The variation of apparent equilibrium constant with the concentration of the external solution and hence with the equivalent fraction of the ion in the resin phase (X_{B_2}) has been shown to be irregular.

In an earlier communication¹ it has been shown for several cation exchangers that the apparent equilibrium constant K_a for cation—hydrogen exchange varies irregularly with the concentration of the external solution and hence with the equivalent fraction of the cation in the resin phase. In the present studies univalent anions: fluoride, chloride, bromide, iodide, and nitrate, have been used to justify a similar conclusion with weakly basic as well as strongly basic anion exchangers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resins that have been used in these studies include Amberlite IR-4B, a weakly basic anion exchanger and Amberlite IRA-410, a strongly basic anion exchanger. These were used in the hydroxyl form for all equilibrium studies.

The stock solutions for anions concerned were prepared by taking the corresponding potassium salts of the B. D. H. AnalaR quality in ion-free water.

Procedure.—The studies were performed by a batch technique at room temperature ($\approx 32^\circ$) in 250 ml pyrex Erlenmeyer flasks provided with air-tight glass stoppers. In each case 100 ml of the solution concerned of the anion of a particular known strength was equilibrated with a known weight (1 g.) of the resin. Intermittent shaking was done to keep the solid and liquid phases well in contact with each other. The weakly basic exchanger attained equilibrium after 7 days, whereas the strongly basic exchanger required not more than an hour to attain perfect equilibrium. After equilibrium was attained, aliquots from the solutions were withdrawn and titrated for alkalinity generated due to exchange of anions with OH^- of the resin. The experiments were carried out over convenient ranges of concentrations of anions in the liquid phase.

After determining the exchange capacities of the resins², the equilibrium constants were calculated by using the expression :

$$K_a = \frac{X_{B_R}}{X_{A_R}} \frac{C_{A_W}}{C_{B_W}}$$

where X_{B_R} and X_{A_R} are the equivalent fractions of the anions concerned in the resin phase and C_{A_W} and C_{B_W} are the corresponding concentrations of anions in the solution phase. An expression similar to this was used by Kressman and Kitchener³ for univalent cations and must also hold good for univalent anions.

FIG. 1. Amberlite IR-4B (OH).

FIG. 2. Amberlite IR-410 (OH).

Graphs were plotted for the variation of K_a versus X_{B_R} in both the cases of weakly and strongly basic resins (see Figs. 1 and 2).

DISCUSSION

It has already been pointed out¹ that exchange affinities in aqueous solution for univalent ions depends chiefly on the concentration of the external solution. The stoichiometric equilibrium constant for an exchange reaction, which is a measure of relative affinity; is thus dependent on the changes in the concentration of external solution and hence X_{B_R} (the equivalent fraction in the resin phase). It is thus a matter of comparison only that a similar effect be observed in anion-equilibrium studies.

2. Heyman and O'Donnell, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1949, 4, 395.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1190.

Figs. 1 and 2 clearly show this irregular variation of K_a with X_{B_2} in all cases of univalent anions on weakly as well as strongly basic exchangers. These observations for anionic studies thus support our own observations with cations and also the observations of Duncan and Lister⁴, Lowen *et al*⁵, and Reichenberg *et al*⁶; and others who believe in inconsistency of exchange-equilibrium constant.

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4. *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1949, 7, 104; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3285.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2666.
6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 493.